

Various factors affecting stability, structure and reactivity of ternary complexes in solution have been extensively dealt by Sigel⁹. From statistical considerations $\log K_{M. \text{bipy}}^M$ is expected to be appreciably less than $\log K_1$, as the concentration of electrons around the metal ion in $(M. \text{bipy})^{2+}$ is more than in $[M(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]^{2+}$ owing to greater coordinating tendency of bipy than that of water.

However, $\log K_1 \approx \log K_{M. \text{bipy}}^M$. This anomaly could perhaps be best explained in terms of indirect interactions (ternary complexes in which the two kinds of ligands 'simply' coordinate to the same metal ion), particularly by way of formation of π bonds⁹. There appears to be $M-N\pi$ interaction on account of back donation of the electrons from metal $d\pi$ -orbital to the vacant delocalized π -orbital over the bipy molecule, in addition to the σ -bond between the two nitrogen atoms of the bipy molecule. Thus, the concentration of electrons around the metal ion in $(M. \text{bipy})^{2+}$ does not increase significantly as a result of which electronegativity of the metal ion in this species remains almost the same as in $[M(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]^{2+}$, which justifies $\log K_1 \approx \log K_{M. \text{bipy}}^M$. On the other hand,

$\log K_{M. \text{bipy}}^M > \log K_2$, may be explained on the basis that during the formation of ML_2 species there is a coulombic repulsion between the negative oxygens of the two ligand anions tending to lower the stability of ML_2 specie, there is no such repulsion in the case of ternary complexes.

A plot of $\log K_{M. \text{bipy}}^M$ versus $\log K_1$ is linear indicating that the process of association of L with $(M. \text{bipy})^{2+}$ species in the ternary system, follows the same pattern as that of the association of L^{2-} with $[M(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]^{2+}$ in the corresponding binary system.

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A Nickel(II) Complex of a New Hydrazone Type Macrocyclic Ligand

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SINCE Melson and Busch¹ reported the efficacy of a metal ion, particularly nickel(II), indicating the synthesis of a macrocyclic ligand through self-condensation of *o*-amino benzaldehyde, a large number of reports have appeared in the literature concerning synthesis of metal chelates of a variety of macrocyclic ligand²⁻⁸. These macrocyclic ligands have all nitrogen⁴, all sulphur⁵, all oxygen⁶, or nitrogen-sulphur⁷ or nitrogen-oxygen as donor centres⁸. We wish to report here a nickel complex of a new macrocyclic ligand(III) prepared by the reaction of *bis*(acetyl acetone) ethylene diimine(II) with carbonylhydrazide(I) in presence of nickel(II) ion.

Experimental

Materials and Methods:

A. Synthesis of the ligands :

(i) *Ethyl ester of carbazic acid* : $\text{H}_2\text{N}-\text{NH}-\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$

Its synthesis and properties have already been described in an earlier paper from this laboratory⁹.

(ii) *Preparation of carbonylhydrazide* : $\text{NH}_2-\text{NH}-\text{CO}-\text{NH}-\text{NH}_2$

This has been described earlier^{9,10}.

(iii) *Preparation of bis(acetylacetone) ethylene diimine* :

This Schiff base was prepared following standard procedure¹¹. (m.p. 111°; lit., m.p. 111.5°).

B. Synthesis of the complex :

(i) *Preparation of tetraphenyl boron salt of the nickel(II) macrocyclic complex.*

Nickel(II) chloride hexahydrate (.005 mole, dissolved in 2 ml rectified spirit) was added to a hot

solution of the carbonylhydrazide (.005 mole) in 40 ml of boiling rectified spirit. During the addition, sky-blue coloured precipitate appeared immediately. This was refluxed for 5 minutes.

Then *bis*(acetylacetonate) ethylene diimine (.005 mole, dissolved in 5 ml rectified spirit) was added to the mixture and refluxing was continued for 7 hours. The initial sky-blue precipitate went into solution with time and a reddish-green solution appeared. It was cooled to room temperature and filtered. The volume of reddish-green solution was reduced by evaporation to one-third. It was again cooled to room temperature and filtered again. The filtrate was treated with excess of anhydrous acetone. A sticky mass along with a red solution appeared. The sticky mass was repeatedly treated with anhydrous acetone till a crystalline product was obtained. This was filtered under suction and washed with hot acetone and dried over silica gel. This crystalline compound was dissolved in rectified spirit and filtered. To this filtrate, appropriate amount of sodium tetraphenyl boron solution (in rectified spirit) was added.

After some time needle-shaped reddish-yellow crystalline product separated out. It was filtered, washed with warm rectified spirit and dried over silica gel.

Found for the dihydrate : N, 8.4 ; Ni, 5.6 ; H₂O 2.6 per cent.

Calc : N, 8.46 ; Ni, 5.9 ; H₂O, 3.0 per cent.

The sample was heated in an oven at 120°, cooled, and then again analysed.

Found : C, 75.45 ; H, 7.1 ; N, 8.7 and Ni 5.8 per cent.

Calc : C, 75.23 ; H, 6.4 ; N, 8.7 and Ni 6.03 per cent.

Analysis and physical measurements :

Nickel was estimated as *bis*(dimethyl glyoximate) nickel(II). Nitrogen was determined by Dumas

method. Magnetic moment was obtained from corrected χ_M values, using a Gouy Balance with CuSO₄·5H₂O as a calibrant. Nujol mull spectrum was run by R.S.I.C., Madras. Solution spectrum was run in Hilger-Uvispek spectrophotometer over the range 350-1000 nm. C & H analysis as also the I.R. spectra were carried out by C.D.R.I., Lucknow. The electrical conductivity was measured by Philips conductivity bridge at 25°.

Results and Discussion

A. *Infrared spectra :*

We have studied the i.r. spectra of *bis*(acetylacetonate) ethylene diimine, carbonylhydrazide and nickel(II) complex of the new macrocyclic ligand.

The absorption bands of *bis*(acetylacetonate) ethylene diimine agree quite well with those reported and assigned by Ueno and Martell^{1,2}. The CH₂, CH₃ absorptions are found as weak and little broad bands within 2950 to 3150 cm⁻¹ while the keto (C=O) and (C=N) appear at 1610 and 1580 cm⁻¹ respectively. The carbonylhydrazide shows bands at 3360, 3200 and 3300 cm⁻¹. These are assigned as the asymmetric (N-H), symmetric (N-H) vibration of the -NH₂ group, and the secondary -NH group^{1,8} respectively. The C=O stretch of the carbonylhydrazide appears as a strong broad absorption band centered at about 1635 cm⁻¹, while the C-N stretch^{1,4} appears as a medium strong band at 915 cm⁻¹. In the nickel(II) macrocyclic complex, the proposed structure(III) calls for a secondary N-H stretch only. In keeping with this only one very strong sharp band appears at 3320 cm⁻¹. We assign this to the secondary N-H stretch. If all the four C=N nitrogens had similar environments and if all of them were coordinated to the metal ion (cf. III), we would have a single stretch for C=N. In reality, the i.r. spectrum of the complex distinctly shows one very strong and broad band centered at 1530 cm⁻¹ which is assigned to C=N stretch in our complex. The broadness probably indicates that we have two different kinds of C=N in the complex. Compared to *bis*(acetylacetonate) ethylene diimine the C=N stretch^{1,5} at